

OUT OF DIRTINESS COMES HAPPINESS: STIGMA, IDENTITY, AND INFORMAL RECYCLING LABOUR IN UMUDIKE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Informal recycling occupations occupy an uncomfortable position in many societies: they are economically necessary yet socially devalued. In Nigeria, scrap collectors are among the workers most exposed to this tension, performing essential waste management functions while enduring public ridicule, avoidance, and moral stigmatisation. This study examines how scrap collectors in Umudike, Abia State, actively resist and reinterpret that stigma. Adopting a qualitative ethnographic approach, the research draws on in-depth interviews and participant observation with 30 collectors and traders, analysed through Clifford Geertz's interpretive framework. Findings reveal that collectors transform what society devalues into sources of economic independence, emotional fulfilment, and social recognition through a process of symbolic inversion. Female participants additionally navigate gendered expectations while asserting autonomy and skill. The study concludes that scrap collection in Umudike is more than a low-status occupation. It is a culturally and emotionally significant practice in which marginalized workers actively construct dignity, identity, and happiness by reinterpreting dirtiness as economic opportunity and moral achievement, refusing the social labels imposed on them. Implications include greater policy recognition of informal collectors, cultural understanding of how meaning-making reshapes perceptions of low-status work, and the value of ethnographic methods for exploring marginalized practices in semi-urban Nigerian contexts.

Keywords: Cultural meaning, Informal work, Scrap collection, Stigma, and Symbolic inversion.

INTRODUCTION

Steel can be sourced from the recycling of scrap ferrous metal (Eze, 2019). A study by Ohimain (2013) revealed that scrap metals constitute significant elements of municipal solid waste in Nigeria, representing 1.8 percent in the South West, 10.8 percent in the South East, and between 3 to 20 percent in the North West. Furthermore, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has reported that for each tone of steel produced from scrap, 1.115 kg of iron ore, 625 kg of coal, and 53 kg of limestone are conserved. Utilising recycled steel results in a 75 percent reduction in energy consumption, a 90 percent decrease in raw material usage, an 86 percent reduction in air pollution, a 40 percent decrease in water usage, a 76 percent reduction in water pollution, and a 97 percent decrease in mining waste. The recycling rates for steel are 95 percent in automobiles, 88 percent in appliances, and 70 percent in steel packaging (Eze, 2019). Although community some leaders frown at some works (Peters and Basse, 2019), research indicates that, unlike plastics, metals, particularly steel, possess indestructible atoms, allowing for repeated recycling: the iron atoms in steel can be re-melted indefinitely without degradation (Eze, 2019). The recycling of scrap metal can be accomplished through various methods; however, certain techniques present numerous challenges that may arise due to the production processes employed or the initial composition of the scrap metal. The processes involved in scrap metal recycling include collection, pre-treatment/sorting, melting, refining the chemistry, and casting the molten metal to create a cast. The primary steelmaking process entails the direct transfer of molten steel from the furnace to the caster, but research has demonstrated that secondary refining (the indirect treatment of molten metal in a ladle or vessel) utilised in steel production provides a multitude of opportunities, including enhanced control over temperature and steel grades/chemistry. This allows for the high production of diverse steel grades with optimal use of alloying compounds and/or elements (Eze, 2019).

Jobs associated with dirt, waste, and pollution are widely treated as low-status work. In many societies, such occupations attract social disapproval because they are linked to ideas of impurity, danger, and low prestige (Hughes, 1958; Ashforth and Kreiner, 1999). Yet these forms of labour remain essential to everyday life, especially in contexts where formal waste management systems are limited. Scrap collectors in Nigeria occupy this difficult position. They contribute to environmental sanitation and material recovery while facing ridicule, avoidance, and moral judgment from the public. In many settings, scrap collection is not only an economic activity but also a socially marked occupation that shapes how workers are perceived and treated. Existing studies show that informal waste workers often experience exclusion and negative labelling (Goffman, 1963; Medina, 2008). Despite this, scrap collectors continue to engage in their work and develop ways of sustaining their livelihoods within challenging social conditions.

This study focuses on scrap collectors in Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria. It examines how they interpret their work, respond to stigma, and construct meaning around what others describe as “dirty” labour. The study is guided by the objective of exploring how scrap collectors reframe dirtiness and stigma into dignity, identity, and happiness. By centring participants' own expressions and experiences, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of how meaning shapes the lived realities of informal work in semi-urban Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Existing research on scrap collection in Nigeria has largely prioritised quantitative and policy concerns, while giving limited attention to the scrap collectors themselves. Studies such as Ogwueleka (2009), Adeyemi *et al.* (2001), Kofoworola (2007), Nzeadibe and Iwuoha (2008), and Iniewe (2013) focus mainly on waste volumes, material composition, economic value, recycling profitability, and institutional frameworks. Much of this work is useful for understanding waste management systems in cities such as Lagos and Ilorin, yet it often leaves out the voices, lived experiences, and interpretive meanings of the workers who collect and trade scrap. This gap is more visible in semi-urban contexts such as Umudike, Abia State, where scrap collection occurs within distinct social, cultural, and economic conditions. There is limited research on how scrap collectors in such settings experience stigma, negotiate public perceptions, and construct dignity and identity through their work. As a result, scrap collection is often treated mainly as an economic activity or environmental service, rather than as a cultural practice shaped by meaning-making.

This limitation restricts scholarly understanding of how stigmatised workers actively reinterpret “dirty work” and resist social devaluation. Preliminary fieldwork in Umudike indicates that scrap collectors do not only endure stigma. They also reframe dirtiness into pride and happiness. This is captured in the expression, “Out of dirtiness comes happiness.” Yet few studies in Nigeria adopt ethnographic or interpretive approaches to examine these “webs of meaning” (Geertz, 1973), including how cultural notions of dirt (Douglas, 1966) and value redefinition (Thompson, 1979) are negotiated from insiders' perspectives. Consequently, scholarship still provides an incomplete understanding of scrap collection in Nigeria, especially in semi-urban communities. Without sustained attention to the symbolic, moral, and identity dimensions of scrap collection, research continues to understate how scrap collectors construct meaning, dignity, and social worth within a stigmatised livelihood.

By adopting Geertz's interpretive lens, this study foregrounds participants' own perspectives, treating their experiences as meaningful texts to be understood. This approach enables insight into how collectors construct identity, pride, and happiness, showing the cultural and moral significance embedded in a work often dismissed as low-status.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Dirty Work and Stigma

Occupations associated with waste, bodily exposure, or moral suspicion are often described as “dirty work” because they attract strong social disapproval (Hughes, 1958; Ashforth and Kreiner, 1999). Such work is not only physically demanding but also socially devalued, as workers are frequently perceived as inferior or undesirable. Stigma operates as a social process through which individuals are discredited and reduced in status because of their association with certain forms of labour (Goffman, 1963). For scrap collectors, this stigma is expressed through ridicule, avoidance, and exclusion from mainstream social spaces.

Research shows that workers in stigmatised occupations do not simply accept these negative labels. They actively construct alternative meanings that protect their sense of self. Ashforth and Kreiner (1999) argue that such workers develop strategies that include reframing their work as valuable, emphasising its social importance, and building strong occupational identities. Simpson *et al.* (2014) further show that workers manage both physical and social stigma by redefining how their work is understood within their

communities. These responses indicate that stigma is negotiated through everyday practices rather than passively endured.

Waste, Value, and Cultural Meaning

Waste carries meanings that extend beyond its material form. Douglas (1966) conceptualises dirt as “matter out of place,” showing that what is considered waste reflects social classifications of order and disorder. This perspective positions scrap collectors as actors who engage directly with materials that society seeks to remove or ignore. Thompson (1979) adds that value is not fixed but changes over time, allowing discarded materials to be transformed into useful and economically valuable resources. Through this process, waste shifts from being seen as useless to becoming a source of livelihood.

Further studies highlight how waste is linked to identity and social relations. Hawkins (2006) and Gille (2007) show that interactions with waste involve ethical considerations, social meanings, and everyday practices through which individuals define themselves. In this sense, scrap collection is not only about material recovery but also about engaging with systems of value, morality, and identity. Collectors operate within these systems by redefining the meaning of discarded objects and, in the process, reshaping how their work is understood.

Informal Waste Work in Nigeria and the Global South

In many developing contexts, informal waste workers play a central role in managing urban waste. Studies across Nigeria show that scrap collectors and waste pickers contribute significantly to recycling, resource recovery, and environmental sustainability (Medina, 2008; Wilson *et al.*, 2006; Nzeadibe and Iwuoha, 2008). Despite this contribution, they often work under difficult conditions, with limited institutional support and persistent social stigma.

Research in Nigerian cities such as Lagos and Ilorin shows that waste workers are often treated as socially inferior because of the nature of their work (Ogwueleka, 2009; Adeyemi *et al.*, 2001). At the same time, these workers develop survival strategies that enable them to sustain their livelihoods. Ajani and Ogunjimi (2012) note that informal waste activities are shaped by economic necessity and create networks of exchange and cooperation among workers. More recent studies indicate that waste workers adopt coping strategies that help them manage stigma and maintain a sense of dignity (Khanal *et al.*, 2023).

These studies provide important insights into the economic and environmental roles of informal waste workers. However, they focus mainly on structural conditions, economic contributions, and policy concerns. Less attention is given to how workers interpret their experiences and construct meaning around their work, especially in semi-urban settings such as Umudike.

Meaning-Making and Symbolic Inversion

Understanding how scrap collectors interpret their work requires an approach that focuses on meaning. Geertz (1973) argues that human action is shaped by webs of significance through which people make sense of their lives. From this perspective, everyday expressions, practices, and symbols provide insight into how individuals interpret their social world. In the context of scrap collection, references to dirt, pride, and happiness are not only descriptive but reflect deeper systems of meaning.

The concept of symbolic inversion further explains how negative social labels are transformed into positive identities. Turner (1969) describes symbolic inversion as a process in which what is socially devalued is reinterpreted as meaningful and valuable. For scrap collectors, this involves redefining dirtiness as a source of income, dignity, and personal achievement. Through such reinterpretation, workers challenge dominant perceptions and construct alternative moral frameworks for understanding their work.

Although existing studies recognise stigma and coping strategies among waste workers, few adopt an interpretive approach that examines how meaning is constructed from the perspective of the workers themselves. This gap is particularly evident in Nigerian research, where limited attention is given to the symbolic and cultural dimensions of scrap collection. This study addresses this gap by focusing on how scrap collectors in Umudike interpret their work and transform stigma into dignity, identity, and happiness.

METHODOLOGY

This paper draws on data from a preliminary phase of a larger ongoing ethnographic study involving 30 scrap collectors in Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria, conducted between August and October 2025. This phase forms part of that broader study on scrap collection livelihoods in Umudike; other dimensions are reported separately.

Ethnographic design was adopted for the study which allowed close engagement with daily routines, social interactions, and personal narratives of scrap collectors. The approach facilitated understanding of the cultural meanings, values, and moral interpretations participants attach to their work. Adopting Geertz's interpretive framework, the study treats scrap collection as a cultural practice through which participants construct meaning and resist stigma.

Participants were selected purposively from the larger study sample, all having at least six months of experience in scrap collection or trading. Selection prioritised collectors who could articulate their experiences with public stigma and their strategies for maintaining dignity. Semi-structured interviews lasted 35-60 minutes and were conducted in Pidgin, English and Igbo, with translations verified by a bilingual research assistant. Interview questions explored daily work routines, experiences with social judgment, emotional responses to stigma, and sources of pride or fulfilment. Participant observation complemented interviews by recording everyday practices at scrap collection sites, including sorting, transporting, weighing, and social exchanges. The researchers engaged in active collection and selling of reclaimed materials alongside participants, enabling detailed insight into their lived experiences and the social dynamics of their work environment.

Data were analysed inductively using thematic coding informed by Geertz's thick description framework. Interview transcripts and field notes were read repeatedly to identify recurring patterns in how participants described their work, managed stigma, and constructed meaning. Initial codes captured specific strategies (selective attention, reframing dirt as opportunity, pride in earnings) and emotional responses (happiness, motivation, dignity). These codes were iteratively compared and refined into broader themes of symbolic inversion and meaning-making.

The researchers maintained reflexivity throughout the study. Conducting daily scrap collection and observation alongside participants provided direct insight into their routines, social interactions, and emotional labour. The researchers occupied a dual position: outsiders to the scrap collection community but insiders to the broader Nigerian social context. This

position shaped interpretation at every stage. Regular member-checking discussions with participants helped validate emerging themes and kept findings grounded in their own perspectives rather than external assumptions.

FINDINGS

Participants described active ways of managing social stigma and redefining work that others consider shameful. A 19-year-old female collector with three years' experience explained that, although many see scrap collection as dirty, she experiences it differently. She emphasised that earning from scrap brings her happiness and pride, turning what others view as dirt into a source of joy and independence. In her words;

"Out of Dirtiness comes happiness"

(In-depth Interview, October 3, 2025).

She elaborated on the reactions she faces and her response to them. Some people tell her that, as a young woman, she should not be doing this work. Others show pity or give small financial gifts. Yet she focuses on the opportunities: the money she earns and the sense of accomplishment from a successful day. For her, the visible dirtiness of the materials does not diminish the value of her work. Rather, it becomes a symbol of productivity and personal fulfilment.

A 21-year-old male collector from Ebem Ohafia explained how he responds to public insults:

"Entering certain spaces, people deride me, assuming my life is hopeless. Instead of discouraging me, these reactions motivate me to work harder and demonstrate my competence" (In-depth Interview, September 26, 2025).

Another participant, a 27-year-old mother from Ideato North with over a year of experience, described a strategy of selective attention. In her narratives, she explained that;

"I focus on the earnings from my work rather than others' negative perceptions. I advise my colleagues to overlook insults and criticisms as long as the work provides income, and that the financial independence protects us from social judgment and the need to beg for a living" (In-depth Interview, October 10, 2025).

One young woman further explained that;

"People see it as dirty business and make bad comments, but me, I see something more than dirtiness. That dirty thing gives money" (In-depth Interview, October 3, 2025).

Another participant, a mother narrated that;

"I ignore social judgment to focus on my earnings. The financial independence protects my dignity and enables me to provide for her family" (In-depth Interview, October 10, 2025).

These accounts show that scrap collectors do not passively accept stigma. They actively reinterpret “dirtiness” as a pathway to financial independence, personal pride, and social dignity, transforming what society devalues into a source of meaning and self-determination.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

A central expression from the field, “to me, out of dirtiness comes happiness,” illustrates how collectors reinterpret what society labels as “dirty work.” In most contexts, dirt signifies shame or low status, yet participants invert this perception. They treat scrap not merely as waste but as a source of pride, livelihood, and personal value. For many collectors, engagement with scrap is both an economic activity and a way to assert self-worth. These narratives show that the work offers more than income; it produces emotional fulfilment, pride, and a sense of moral achievement. From an interpretive perspective, these findings align with Geertz's (1973) view that cultural symbols encode deeper meaning. Dirt and scrap, though socially coded as negative, function as symbols of agency, resilience, and social identity. The process of symbolic inversion (Turner, 1969) is visible as collectors transform stigma into dignity and happiness. Douglas's (1966) “matter out of place” theory also provides insight, showing that what society treats as disorder or impurity is actively reframed by participants into opportunity and value. Ashforth and Kreiner (1999) similarly note that workers in stigmatised occupations often construct pride and moral legitimacy in the very roles others disdain.

Gendered experiences further shape these reinterpretations. Female collectors frequently navigate additional societal expectations, such as assumptions about what women should do, yet they consistently assert autonomy and skill through their work. Their strategies, including selective attention to insults, collective support, and focus on earnings, highlight how emotional fulfilment intersects with resistance to both gendered and occupational stigma. Scrap collectors in other Nigerian cities and international contexts show similar patterns of stigma resistance. In Lagos, informal waste pickers face social derision but develop coping mechanisms and identity-protection strategies (Khanal *et al.*, 2023). Internationally, Garcia-Lorenzo *et al.* (2022) highlight that marginalised groups actively resist the stigmatizing tendencies of dominant groups. In Umudike, participants achieve this by using discarded materials, or “akpakara,” to reclaim social worth, illustrating both local and global patterns of everyday resistance.

The findings of this study have practical, cultural, and research implications. Practically, recognising scrap collection as socially and culturally meaningful can inform policy by promoting better support for informal collectors and integrating them into municipal waste management systems, while acknowledging their dignity and agency may help reduce stigma and enhance participation in local economies. Culturally, the study shows how meaning-making transforms social perceptions of work, as symbolic inversion enables individuals and communities to redefine what is considered low-status, linking labour to pride, identity, and moral value. For research, the paper highlights the importance of ethnographic approaches in understanding stigmatised work, suggesting future studies could explore comparative perspectives across other semi-urban and urban contexts in Nigeria or track changes in stigma perception over time.

CONCLUSION

Scrap collectors in Umudike are actively transforming work that is socially stigmatised into a source of pride, emotional fulfilment, and moral agency. Through symbolic inversion, they reinterpret “dirtiness” as economic opportunity, personal dignity, and happiness. Participants' narratives show that marginalised workers negotiate identity and meaning within everyday social life, highlighting the complex interplay between livelihood, stigma, and self-worth.

The findings underscore that scrap collection is more than a low-status occupation. It is a culturally and emotionally significant practice in which economic survival, social identity, and moral reasoning intersect. By centring participants' perspectives, this study illustrates how meaning-making reshapes dominant social perceptions of work and provides insight into the resilience, agency, and dignity embedded in marginalised livelihoods.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are made. Government agencies like the Abia State Environmental Protection Agency (ASEPA), Abia State Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Local Government Authorities, and Community Leaders should:

1. Launch awareness campaigns featuring collectors' own voices and narratives. Use their expressions like “out of dirtiness comes happiness” to challenge stigma and help society recognise scrap collection as dignified, honest labour that contributes to environmental sustainability.
2. Provide financial support that honours dignity through fair pricing structures, accessible microfinance, and protection from exploitation. Frame support as recognition of valuable work, not charity. Ensure that interventions preserve the autonomy, independence, and moral frameworks that collectors identify as central to their happiness and self-worth.
3. If possible, partner with Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike (MOUAU) and the Recyclers Association of Nigeria (RAN), Abia State Branch, to establish collector led training programs on safety, sorting efficiency, and market linkages. This approach uses academic resources and industry experience to formalize skills, reduce health risks, and raise occupational prestige while maintaining autonomy.

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